

ENERHAT

ENERHAT

- ENERHAT (Energy Housing Assessment Tool) is an application that enables tenants, owners and real estate agents to obtain information on energy labels and the state of conservation of residential buildings, to compare the energy efficiency of the dwellings with similar buildings, to assess the investment needed to carry out improvements and finally to apply for subsidies to undertake the reform
- The application integrates the data obtained from the Energy Performance Certificates provided by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN), the building technical inspections facilitated by the Catalan Agency for Housing (AHC), the cadastre and the census sections, together with geographic information
- The rehabilitation measures are based on the ICAEN simulation tool and the "Long-term strategy for energy rehabilitation in the building sector in Spain" (ERESEE 2014)

Enerhat says:

Are you a homeowner? Do you want to know how you can improve the energy efficiency of the building? How much would it cost and how much would you save? Where would you get public subsidies to undertake the reform?

Enerhat says:

Do you want to buy or sell an apartment? Do you need to know the state of conservation of the building? Do you want to know the apartment's energy class and compare it with similar buildings?

Enerhat says:

ENERHAT provides you with the answers to these questions

Enerhat says:

Are you a homeowner? Do you want to know how you can improve the energy efficiency of the building? How much would it cost and how much would you save? Where would you get public subsidies to undertake the reform?

Enerhat says:

Do you want to buy or sell an apartment? Do you need to know the state of conservation of the building? Do you want to know the apartment's energy class and compare it with similar buildings?

Enerhat says:

ENERHAT provides you with the answers to these questions

User says:

I would like to buy an apartment and I would like to know the state of the building before making the investment. What do I need to know?

Enerhat says:

First, I recommend you find out if the building has passed the building technical inspection and if it the apartment has an Energy Performance Certificate

Enerhat says:

Once we know the building's condition, we can see if it is necessary to undertake a rehabilitation to improve its energy efficiency

Enerhat says:

ENERHAT helps you find it out, step by step

User says:

I would like to buy an apartment and I would like to know the state of the building before making the investment. What do I need to know?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFINISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Enter the address of the building:

Name of the municipality 🔍 Name of the road 🔍 Num. 🔍

Enerhat says:

You have to follow these steps. First, you must enter the address of the building: town, street and number

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REPAIR/RENEWAL MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Enter the address of the building:

BARCELONA (BARCELONA) BRUC (CL) 85

The indicated address corresponds to a building located at CL BRUC 85

Building located at CL BRUC 85

- The building does not have a technical inspection report
- The building does not have Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)

Please select a dwelling:

ATTENTION: The addresses of some buildings are written differently in the various databases. Because of this, the same dwelling might be listed several times with the address written in various formats

CL BRUC N.85 It has energy performance certificate	c/ Bruch, 85, 4o-1a. It has energy performance certificate
c/ Bruc, 85, 1o-2a. It has energy performance certificate	c/ Bruch, 85, Ppal 1a. It has energy performance certificate

Enerhat says:

You have to follow these steps. First, you must enter the address of the building: town, street and number

Enerhat says:

In the upper part, we can see if the building has an Energy Performance Certificate and if the technical inspection has been carried out

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

Progress bar: 1. DWELLING (active), 2. ENERGY INDICATORS, 3. REFURBISHMENT MEASURES, 4. SUBSIDIES, 5. FINAL REPORT

Enter the address of the building:

BARCELONA (BARCELONA) [search] BRUC (CL) [search] 85 [search]

The indicated address corresponds to a building located at CL BRUC 85

Building located at CL BRUC 85

- The building does not have a technical inspection report
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Enerhat says:

You have to follow these steps. First, you must enter the address of the building: town, street and number

Enerhat says:

In the upper part, we can see if the building has an Energy Performance Certificate and if the technical inspection has been carried out

Enerhat says:

In the lower part, the apartments contained in the selected building are listed. Here you can see if the apartments have an Energy Performance Certificate or not

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

This is the report of the building technical inspection according to the information provided by AHC:

A building technical inspection report was not found

Deadline obtaining: This building should have passed the technical inspection

ENERHAT recommends taking advantage of the need to rehabilitate the building to apply energy-saving measures.

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO₂ emissions

The rating is very low

Compare with similar buildings

Environmental Impact

Energy consumption

The rating is very low

Compare with similar buildings

Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

In the second step, detailed information of the selected apartment is shown

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

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CO2 emissions

59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.

Energy consumption

314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

In the second step, detailed information of the selected apartment is shown

Enerhat says:

ENERHAT provides a summary with data from the building technical inspection report and from the Energy Performance Certificate. With this information, a preliminary assessment of the state of the apartment can be made

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others Combined measures

Walls
Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate. ⓘ

ENERHAT proposes:

- To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the air chamber or in the interior space.

ATTENTION: The values are for a building. ⓘ

	Ahorro energía ⓘ	Ahorro económico ⓘ	Inversión ⓘ	Mantenimiento ⓘ	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión ⓘ	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión ⓘ
Colocación de aislamiento por el exterior de la fachada.	19 - 21%	1.085 - 1.178 €/any	15.228 - 22.640 €	1.440 €/any	14 - 19 anys	8 - 13 anys
Colocación de aislamiento por el interior de la fachada.	10 - 12%	572 - 679 €/any	5.523 - 8.599 €	1.440 €/any	9 - 13 anys	8 - 12 anys

Enerhat says:

In the third step, information on the current state of the building and the proposed rehabilitation measures for each constructive element (walls, roofs, windows, etc.) are provided

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

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Enerhat says:

In the third step, information on the current state of the building and the proposed rehabilitation measures for each constructive element (walls, roofs, windows, etc.) are provided

Enerhat says:

Following a diagnosis of the state of the building, ENERHAT proposes a series of rehabilitation measures to reduce energy consumption

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES **SUBSIDIES** FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Subsidies for building renewal

Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona

City of Barcelona December 31, 2016 Up to 50% subsidies

IDAE Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la energía

Spain Deadline closed Up to 70% subsidies

Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya

All the municipalities of Catalonia except Barcelona Deadline closed Up to 50% subsidies

Consorci metropolità de l'habitatge

All the municipalities of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, except Barcelona Deadline closed From 35% to 50% subsidies

Consorci de l'habitatge de l'àrea metropolitana de barcelona

Enerhat says:

Then, in the fourth step, ENERHAT offers information on subsidies from public bodies to carry out the rehabilitation work

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Imprimir Informe

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Rehabilita el teu habitatge
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laSalle
RAMÓN LLULL UNIVERSITY

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Caracteristiques

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
ATTENTION: The certificates processed before January 16, 2016 have been re-qualified by ICAEN. For this reason, the values of the certificate (original) and the one that appears in ENERHAT (requisites) may be different.
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
ATTENTION: The certificates processed before January 16, 2016 have been re-qualified by ICAEN. For this reason, the values of the certificate (original) and the one that appears in ENERHAT (requisites) may be different.
Cadastral reference: [0431613DF3803A00010E](#)
Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

Enerhat dice:

At the end of the process, you can save all the information facilitated in each step

ENERHAT

Step 1: State of the building

The screenshot displays the ENERHAT web application interface. At the top, the logo 'ENERHAT' is followed by the subtitle 'Rehabilitate your dwelling'. Below this is a horizontal progress bar with four steps: 'DWELLING' (marked with a green circle and the number 1), 'ENERGY INDICATORS' (marked with a green circle and the number 2), 'REFURBISHMENT MEASURES' (marked with a green circle and the number 3), and 'SUBSIDIES' (marked with a green circle and the number 4). The 'DWELLING' step is currently active. Below the progress bar, the main content area is titled 'Enter the address of the building:'. This area contains three input fields for address information: 'Name of the municipality', 'Name of the road', and 'Number of the house'. Each input field has a search icon (magnifying glass) to its right.

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING 1 ENERGY INDICATORS 2 REFINISHMENT MEASURES 3 SUBSIDIES 4 FINAL REPORT 5

Enter the address of the building:

Name of the municipality 🔍 Name of the road 🔍 Num. 🔍

User says:

I have found an apartment I am interested in. It is in Bruc Street, in Barcelona

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING 1 ENERGY INDICATORS 2 REFINISHMENT MEASURES 3 SUBSIDIES 4 FINAL REPORT 5

Enter the address of the building:

Name of the municipality 🔍 Name of the road 🔍 Num. 🔍

User says:

I have found an apartment I am interested in. It is in Bruc Street, in Barcelona

Enerhat says:

Please introduce the address and let us see what information we find

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING 1
ENERGY INDICATORS 2
REFURBISHMENT MEASURES 3
SUBSIDIES 4
FINAL REPORT 5

Enter the address of the building:

The indicated address corresponds to a building located at CL BRUC 85

Building located at CL BRUC 85

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Please select a dwelling:

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User says:

I have found an apartment I am interested in. It is in Bruc Street, in Barcelona

Enerhat says:

Please introduce the address and let us see what information we find

User says:

Yes, this is the building

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REPAIR/REPLACEMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

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in. It is in Bruc Street, in Barcelona

Enerhat says:

Please introduce the address and let us see what information we find

User says:

Yes, this is the building

Enerhat says:

Here you can see if the building has an Energy Performance Certificate and if it has passed the building technical inspection

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING | ENERGY INDICATORS | REPAIR/RENEWAL MEASURES | SUBSIDIES | FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

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Please introduce the address and let us see what information we find

User says:

Yes, this is the building

Enerhat says:

Here you can see if the building has an Energy Performance Certificate and if it has passed the building technical inspection

Enerhat says:

Now you have to select the apartment you are interested in to find out what condition it is in

ENERHAT

Step 2: Apartment conditions

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINANCING

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

This is the report of the building technical inspection according to the information provided by AHC:

A building technical inspection report was not found

Deadline obtaining: This building should have passed the technical inspection

ENERHAT recommends taking advantage of the need to rehabilitate the building to apply energy-saving measures

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO₂ emissions

G 59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.

Energy consumption

G 314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

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Energy consumption

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User says:
What condition is the building in?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

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User says:

What condition is the building in?

Enerhat says:

The building does not have the building inspection technical report; you should contact the Catalan Agency for Housing

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

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User says:
What condition is the building in?

Enerhat says:
The building does not have the building inspection technical report; you should contact the Catalan Agency for Housing

User says:
What exactly is this report?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

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Enerhat says:

The building does not have the building inspection technical report; you should contact the Catalan Agency for Housing

User says:

What exactly is this report?

Enerhat says:

A brief explanation can be found by placing the cursor over the question mark

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

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User says:

What exactly is this report?

Enerhat says:

A brief explanation can be found by placing the cursor over the question mark

User says:

Perfect. What does this graph represent? Does it have to do with energy certification?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

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Enerhat says:

A brief explanation can be found by placing the cursor over the question mark

User says:

Perfect. What does this graph represent? Does it have to do with energy certification?

Enerhat says:

Indeed, it indicates the carbon emissions that the apartment generates

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Rehabilitate your dwelling

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User says:

Perfect. What does this graph represent?
Does it have to do with energy certification?

Enerhat says:

Indeed, it indicates the carbon emissions that the apartment generates

User says:

What does the letter "G" mean?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

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This is the report of the building technical inspection according to the information provided by AHC:

A building technical inspection report was not found

Deadline obtaining: This building should have passed the technical inspection

ENERHAT recommends taking advantage of the need to rehabilitate the building to apply energy-saving measures.

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO2 emissions

G 59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.

Energy consumption

G 314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

Indeed, it indicates the carbon emissions that the apartment generates

User says:

What does the letter "G" mean?

Enerhat says:

The certifications can have an A, B, C, D, E, F and G label. The G label corresponds to the highest level of emissions

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
 Area: 1098.6 m²
 Climatic zone: C2
 Use: Plurifamiliar
 Number of floors: 1
 Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
 CO2 emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
 Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
 Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

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- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

User says:

What does the letter "G" mean?

Enerhat says:

The certifications can have an A, B, C, D, E, F and G label. The G label corresponds to the highest level of emissions

User says:

And why are these two graphs alike?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
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- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

The certifications can have an A, B, C, D, E, F and G label. The G label corresponds to the highest level of emissions

User says:

And why are these two graphs alike?

Enerhat says:

The graph on the left corresponds to carbon emissions, and the graph on the right to energy consumption

of emissions

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
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Energy consumption

G 314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

User says:

And why are these two graphs alike?

Enerhat says:

The graph on the left corresponds to carbon emissions, and the graph on the right to energy consumption

Enerhat says:

Carbon emissions reflect the environmental impact of the building in operation. The G label indicates that its impact is very high

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
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CO₂ emissions

Energy consumption

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- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

The graph on the left corresponds to carbon emissions, and the graph on the right to energy consumption

Enerhat says:

Carbon emissions reflect the environmental impact of the building in operation. The G label indicates that its impact is very high

Enerhat says:

In the classification according to the energy consumption, heating, cooling and hot water are taken into account. The G indicates that the energy consumption is very high

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

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CO2 emissions

Energy consumption

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.
- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

Carbon emissions reflect the environmental impact of the building in operation. The G label indicates that its impact is very high

Enerhat says:

In the classification according to the energy consumption, heating, cooling and hot water are taken into account. The G indicates that the energy consumption is very high

User says:

So what does this classification have to do with energy bills?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
 Area: 1098.6 m²
 Climatic zone: C2
 Use: Plurifamiliar
 Number of floors: 1
 Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
 CO2 emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
 Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
 Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

This is the report of the building technical inspection according to the information provided by AHC:

A building technical inspection report was not found.

Deadline obtaining: This building should have passed the technical inspection.

ENERHAT recommends taking advantage of the need to rehabilitate the building to apply energy-saving measures.

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO2 emissions

G 59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental impact.

Energy consumption

G 314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

Enerhat says:

In the classification according to the energy consumption, heating, cooling and hot water are taken into account. The G indicates that the energy consumption is very high

User says:

So what does this classification have to do with energy bills?

Enerhat says:

Here you have a brief explanation

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Construction year: 1894
 Area: 1098.6 m²
 Climatic zone: C2
 Use: Plurifamiliar
 Number of floors: 1
 Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
 CO2 emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
 Cadastral reference: 0431613DF3803A00010E
 Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

This is the report of the building technical inspection according to the information provided by AHC:

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Deadline obtaining: This building should have passed the technical inspection

ENERHAT recommends taking advantage of the need to rehabilitate the building to apply energy-saving measures.

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO2 emissions

59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental Impact.

Energy consumption

314.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

User says:

So what does this classification have to do with energy bills?

Enerhat says:

Here you have a brief explanation

Enerhat says:

Keep in mind that the consumptions that appear in the Energy Performance Certificate have been calculated for a standard usage. For example, keeping a house at 24°C in wintertime would require more energy than the one determined by the energy certification, which considers a standard temperature of 21°C

Here you have a brief explanation

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN) 📌

CO2 emissions 📌

G 59.25 kg/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental impact.

Energy consumption 📌

G 214.38 kWh/m²

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

The following graph shows a classification of buildings with similar characteristics: year of construction, living space, number of floors, climatic zone and use (single/multi-family).

← DWELLING REFURBISHMENT MEASURES →

**The data are obtained from the cadastre, the databases of the Catalan Housing Agency and from the energy performance certificates databases and building energy

Enerhat says:

Keep in mind that the consumptions that appear in the Energy Performance Certificate have been calculated for a standard usage. For example, keeping a house at 24°C in wintertime would require more energy than the one determined by the energy certification, which considers a standard temperature of 21°C

Enerhat says:

This graph enables us to compare the performance of the apartment with the performance of buildings with similar characteristics. Most of them have a higher rating than this apartment, that is to say, they consume less energy

ENERHAT

Rehabilitate your dwelling

These are the energy indicators of the dwelling in relation to those of similar dwellings, according to the data facilitated by the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN)

CO2 emissions

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Environmental impact.

Energy consumption

- The rating is very low
- Compare with similar buildings
- Security and cost of energy supply

The following graph shows a classification of buildings with similar characteristics: year of construction, living space, number of floors, climatic zone and use (single/multi-family).

[← DWELLING](#)

[REFURBISHMENT MEASURES →](#)

**The data are obtained from the cadastre, the databases of the Catalan Housing Agency and from the energy performance certificates databases and building energy

usage. For example, keeping a house at 24°C in wintertime would require more energy than the one determined by the energy certification, which considers a standard temperature of 21°C

Enerhat says:

This graph enables us to compare the performance of the apartment with the performance of buildings with similar characteristics. Most of them have a higher rating than this apartment, that is to say, they consume less energy

User says:

Therefore, this building would need to be renovated to improve its energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption

This graph enables us to compare the performance of the apartment with the performance of buildings with similar characteristics. Most of them have a higher rating than this apartment, that is to say, they consume less energy

User says:

Therefore, this building would need to be renovated to improve its energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption

Enerhat says:

Indeed. Let us see the rehabilitation measures proposed by ENERHAT

ENERHAT

Step 3: Rehabilitation measures to be applied

The screenshot displays the ENERHAT web application interface. At the top, the title 'ENERHAT' is followed by the subtitle 'Rehabilitate your dwelling'. A progress bar below the title shows four steps: 'DWELLING', 'ENERGY INDICATORS', 'REFURBISHMENT MEASURES' (which is the active step, indicated by a green circle with the number 3), and 'SUBSIDIES'. Below the progress bar, the main content area is titled 'Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures'. A text block states: 'ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone)'. Below this, there is a horizontal menu of icons representing different building components: Walls, Roofs, Windows, Systems, Solar panels, Others, and Combined measures. The 'Walls' icon is selected. Under the 'Walls' section, the text reads: 'Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate.' Below this, it says 'ENERHAT proposes:' followed by a list item: 'To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the chamber or in the interior space.' At the bottom of the screenshot, a table is partially visible with the following columns: 'Ahorro energía', 'Ahorro económico', 'Inversión', 'Mantenimiento', and 'Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión'. The table contains data for the measure 'Colocación de aislamiento por el exterior de la fachada'.

	Ahorro energía	Ahorro económico	Inversión	Mantenimiento	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión
Colocación de aislamiento por el exterior de la fachada.	19 - 21%	1.085 - 1.178 €/any	15.238 - 22.640 €	1.440 €/any	14 - 19 anys

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others Combined measures

Walls
Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate. ⓘ

ENERHAT proposes:

- To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the air chamber or in the interior space.

ATTENTION: The values are for a building. ⓘ

	Ahorro energía ⓘ	Ahorro económico ⓘ	Inversión ⓘ	Mantenimiento ⓘ	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión ⓘ	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión ⓘ
Colocación de aislamiento por el exterior de la fachada.	19 - 21%	1.085 - 1.178 €/any	15.228 - 22.640 €	1.440 €/any	14 - 19 anys	8 - 13 anys
Colocación de aislamiento por el interior de la fachada.	10 - 12%	572 - 679 €/any	5.523 - 8.599 €	1.440 €/any	9 - 13 anys	8 - 12 anys

Enerhat says:

Here are the rehabilitation measures for this building

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others Combined measures

Walls
Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate. ⓘ

ENERHAT proposes:

- To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the air chamber or in the interior space.

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	Ahorro energía ⓘ	Ahorro económico ⓘ	Inversión ⓘ	Mantenimiento ⓘ	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión ⓘ	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión ⓘ
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Enerhat says:

Here are the rehabilitation measures for this building

Enerhat says:

One of them is to improve the insulation of the walls

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

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ENERHAT proposes:

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	Ahorro energía ⓘ	Ahorro económico ⓘ	Inversión ⓘ	Mantenimiento ⓘ	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión ⓘ	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión ⓘ
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Enerhat says:

Here are the rehabilitation measures for this building

Enerhat says:

One of them is to improve the insulation of the walls

User says:

OK, what can be done?

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others Combined measures

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ENERHAT proposes:

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	Ahorro energía ⓘ	Ahorro económico ⓘ	Inversión ⓘ	Mantenimiento ⓘ	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión ⓘ	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión ⓘ
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Enerhat says:

Here are the rehabilitation measures for this building

Enerhat says:

One of them is to improve the insulation of the walls

User says:

OK, what can be done?

Enerhat says:

If the wall is insulated on the outside, more energy is saved, but the cost is higher

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone):

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others Combined measures

Walls
Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate.

ENERHAT proposes:

- To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the air chamber or in the interior space.

ATTENTION: The values are for a building.

	Ahorro energía	Ahorro económico	Inversión	Mantenimiento	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión
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Colocación de aislamiento por el interior de la fachada.	10 - 12%	572 - 679 €/any	5.523 - 8.599 €	1.440 €/any	9 - 13 anys	8 - 12 anys

Enerhat says:

One of them is to improve the insulation of the walls

User says:

OK, what can be done?

Enerhat says:

If the wall is insulated on the outside, more energy is saved, but the cost is higher

User says:

I do not know if we can invest a lot in the reform

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS **REFURBISHMENT MEASURES** SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone)

Walls Roofs Windows Systems Solar panels Others **Combined measures**

Combined measures
By implementing combined refurbishment measures it is possible to achieve greater energy savings and to have access to more subsidies.

ENERHAT proposes:

- Packages of measures to improve walls, roofs and windows
- Packages of measures to improve walls, roofs and windows, and to replace the boiler
- Package of low cost measures

ATTENTION: The values are for a building.

	Ahorro energía	Ahorro económico	Inversión	Mantenimiento	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión
Paquete 1: Aislamiento de fachada para el exterior + aislamiento de cubierta para el interior + ventanas PVC y vidrio bajo emisivo.	36,4 %	2.029,4 €/año	40.459,7 €	1.440 €/año	19,9 años	11,1 años
Paquete 2: Aislamiento de fachada para el interior + aislamiento de cubierta para el interior + ventanas PVC y vidrio bajo emisivo.	26,6 %	1.501 €/año	30.901,3 €	1.440 €/año	20,6 años	12,8 años

Enerhat says:

If the wall is insulated on the outside, more energy is saved, but the cost is higher

User says:

I do not know if we can invest a lot in the reform

Enerhat says:

Several rehabilitation measures can be combined to reduce the cost. In addition, more public subsidies can be obtained for rehabilitation if you combine several measures

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

Characteristics of the dwelling and refurbishment measures ⓘ

ENERHAT suggests the following refurbishment measures according to the building characteristics (single/multi-family use, year of construction and climate zone)

Walls | Roofs | Windows | Systems | Solar panels | Others | Combined measures

Walls
Taking into account the building's construction year, it probably lacks insulation in the outer walls or the insulation level is inadequate.

ENERHAT proposes:

- To place insulation on the outer walls. Depending on the characteristics of the wall, it might be more effective to place the insulation outside, inside the air chamber or in the interior space.

ATTENTION: The values are for a building.

	Ahorro energía	Ahorro económico	Inversión	Mantenimiento	Periodo de regreso simple de la inversión	Periodo de regreso de sobrecoste de la inversión
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Indicadors energètics | Subvencions

**The data are obtained from the cadastre, the databases of the Catalan Housing Agency and from the energy performance certificates databases and building energy refurbishment measures simulator of the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN). Last update: March 2017.

If the wall is insulated on the outside, more energy is saved, but the cost is higher

User says:

I do not know if we can invest a lot in the reform

Enerhat says:

Several rehabilitation measures can be combined to reduce the cost. In addition, more public subsidies can be obtained for rehabilitation if you combine several measures

Enerhat says:

We are going to look at the subsidies offered by public bodies

ENERHAT

Step 4: Subsidies for reform

The screenshot displays the ENERHAT website interface. At the top, the logo 'ENERHAT' is followed by the text 'Rehabilitate your dwelling'. Below this is a progress bar with four steps: 'DWELLING' (1), 'ENERGY INDICATORS' (2), 'REFURBISHMENT MEASURES' (3), and 'SUBSIDIES' (4), which is currently selected and highlighted in green. The main content area is titled 'Subsidies for building renewal' and contains four cards, each representing a different subsidy program. Each card includes a title, a location pin icon, a calendar icon, and a hand icon, along with specific details about the program's scope, deadline, and subsidy amount.

Organization	Location	Deadline	Subsidy Amount
Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona	City of Barcelona	December 31, 2016	Up to 50% subsidies
IDAE Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la energía	Spain	Deadline closed	Up to 70% subsidies
Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya	All the municipalities of Catalonia except Barcelona	Deadline closed	Up to 50% subsidies
Consorci metropolità de l'habitatge	All the municipalities of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, except Barcelona	Deadline closed	From 35% to 50% subsidies

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES **SUBSIDIES** FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Subsidies for building renewal

Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona

City of Barcelona December 31, 2016 Up to 50% subsidies

IDAE Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la energía

Spain Deadline closed Up to 70% subsidies

Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya

All the municipalities of Catalonia except Barcelona Deadline closed Up to 50% subsidies

Consorci metropolità de l'habitatge

All the municipalities of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, except Barcelona Deadline closed From 35% to 50% subsidies

Consorci de l'habitatge de l'àrea metropolitana de barcelona

Enerhat says:

These are some of the subsidies offered by public bodies. Let us see if the Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona has an open call

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DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES **SUBSIDIES** FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Subsidies for building renewal

Organization	Location	Deadline	Subsidy Amount
Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona	City of Barcelona	December 31, 2016	Up to 50% subsidies
IDAE Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la energía	Spain	Deadline closed	Up to 70% subsidies
Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya	All the municipalities of Catalonia except Barcelona	Deadline closed	Up to 50% subsidies
Consorci metropolità de l'habitatge	All the municipalities of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, except Barcelona	Deadline closed	From 35% to 50% subsidies
Consorci de l'habitatge de l'àrea metropolitana de barcelona			

Enerhat says:

These are some of the subsidies offered by public bodies. Let us see if the Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona has an open call

User says:

ENERHAT has provided me with valuable information that I would like to keep, how could I do it?

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City of Barcelona | December 31, 2016 | Up to 50% subsidies

Spain | Deadline closed | Up to 70% subsidies

Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya
All the municipalities of Catalonia except Barcelona | Deadline closed | Up to 50% subsidies

Consorci metropolità de l'habitatge
All the municipalities of the metropolitan area of Barcelona, except Barcelona | Deadline closed | From 35% to 50% subsidies

Consorci de l'habitatge de l'àrea metropolitana de barcelona
All municipalities in the metropolitan area of Barcelona | December 31, 2017 | Up to 50% subsidies

← Mesures de rehabilitació | Informe final →

**The data are obtained from the cadastre, the databases of the Catalan Housing Agency and from the energy performance certificates databases and building energy refurbishment measures simulator of the Catalan Institute of Energy (ICAEN). Last update: March 2017.

Enerhat says:

These are some of the subsidies offered by public bodies. Let us see if the Consorci de l'Habitatge de Barcelona has an open call

User says:

ENERHAT has provided me with valuable information that I would like to keep, how could I do it?

Enerhat says:

It is very easy. ENERHAT generates a report with the information facilitated in each step

ENERHAT

Step 5: Final report

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the ENERHAT final report. The browser's address bar is empty. The page has a dark blue header with the ENERHAT logo and the tagline 'Rehabilitate your dwelling'. Below the header is a navigation bar with five steps: 1. DWELLING, 2. ENERGY INDICATORS, 3. REFURBISHMENT MEASURES, 4. SUBSIDIES, and 5. FINANCING. Step 1 is highlighted with a green circle. The main content area features a white box with the ENERHAT logo and tagline in Spanish: 'Rehabilita el teu habitatge'. Below this is the title 'Dwelling in CL BRUC 85' and a photograph of a building. At the bottom, there is a section titled 'Caracteristiques' with the following details: Construction year: 1894, Area: 1098.6 m2, Climatic zone: C1, Use: Plurifamiliar, and Number of floors: 1.

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DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINANCING

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Rehabilita el teu habitatge
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RAMON LLULL UNIVERSITY

Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Caracteristiques

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m2
Climatic zone: C1
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1

ENERHAT
Rehabilitate your dwelling

DWELLING ENERGY INDICATORS REFURBISHMENT MEASURES SUBSIDIES FINAL REPORT

1 2 3 4 5

Imprimir Informe

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Dwelling in CL BRUC 85

Caracteristiques

Construction year: 1894
Area: 1098.6 m²
Climatic zone: C2
Use: Plurifamiliar
Number of floors: 1
Energy consumption: 314.38 kWh/m²
ATTENTION: The certificates processed before January 16, 2016 have been re-qualified by ICAEN. For this reason, the values of the certificate (original) and the one that appears in ENERHAT (requisites) may be different.
CO₂ emissions: 59.25 kg/m²
ATTENTION: The certificates processed before January 16, 2016 have been re-qualified by ICAEN. For this reason, the values of the certificate (original) and the one that appears in ENERHAT (requisites) may be different.
Cadastral reference: [0431613DF3803A00010E](#)
Date of issuance of the energy performance certificate: 9/11/2016

Enerhat says:

This is the report to print or to save

Enerhat says:

I hope we have cleared up any issues you may have had. For more information, please write to arc@salle.url.edu

Enerhat says:

I hope we have cleared up any issues you may have had. For more information, please write to arc@salle.url.edu

User says:

Thanks, and see you soon

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arc.salleurl.edu